

Settlements and Rivers: Overcoming an Ambivalent Relationship from the Perspective of History Didactics

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The study examines the potential of instructional figures as a didactic approach to history education grounded in a meta-level learning about the past, understood as a reflective relationship between historical knowledge, students' lived experience and contemporary global challenges. The study argues that history education oriented toward such a meta-level can move beyond the reproduction of fixed historical narratives and instead support continuous inquiry into the meaning of learning about the past in the present. The theoretical framework is situated within the interdisciplinary debate on the Anthropocene, conceptualized not only as a proposed geological epoch but also as an analytical framework that challenges the conventional separation between human history and natural history. As a didactic response to this framework, the eco-educational project *The Story of the River* is presented as a model that primarily develops core subject-specific competencies in history education while simultaneously encouraging a non-anthropocentric perspective on the river as a historical and cultural entity connecting people, places and multiple forms of life. The study also raises broader questions regarding curriculum design in history education, particularly in relation to sustainability and contemporary societal challenges.

Keywords: river; city; Anthropocene; history didactics; curriculum; non-anthropocentrism; sustainable development.

Introduction

Constructing the presentation of the past for pupils and students in history lessons at primary and secondary schools is a highly specialized process – one that is both essential and indispensable for maintaining a democratic society. It is indispensable because there are numerous sources through which we encounter historical information;¹ however, the only institutionalized form of creating, transmitting and preserving historical consciousness,² at least, that every citizen encounters (author's note), is

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1 We teachers are no longer the exclusive bearers of information about the past; on the contrary, we have become part of a mosaic of diverse information sources and of the various ways in which the past is used, interpreted and even misused. Therefore, the teaching of history should equip students with the ability to discern the quality – that is, the truthfulness, accuracy, and legitimacy – of the wide range of information about history available today. KRATOCHVÍL, *Metafora stromu*, 67.

2 The term "historical consciousness" can be understood as "the individual and collective understanding of the past, the cognitive and cultural factors that shape this understanding, and the relationship of this understanding to the present and the future". *Definition of Historical Consciousness*, <http://www.cshc.ubc.ca/about/> [accessed 15 August 2024]. For the purposes of school history education, the concept of historical consciousness is clearly explained by Viliam Kratochvíl, who defines it as "the mental cognitive, emotional, conscious, and unconscious operations through which historical experience, in the form of memory, is used to orient oneself in contemporary life". LABISCHOVÁ, *Co si uchováme v paměti?* 35; cited in KRATOCHVÍL, *Metafora stromu*, 17.

school-based history education.³ It is essential because there is no other way to understand what the loss of democracy or the loss of fundamental human rights would mean for our present than to look at what such losses meant for us in the past. There is thus no other means of comprehending our present and possible future than by examining that of which our present is the result. For this reason, it is both necessary and desirable to constantly ask the following: What is the aim of learning about the past? What meaning does school history hold for our present? What place does history as a subject occupy within the state curriculum? What is the quality of history education in the Slovak context? Which teaching methods and resources are most or least effective for understanding the past? What is the availability and quality of history textbooks? And finally, what is the quality of teacher training for future history educators and of continuing education for practicing history teachers?⁴

This kind of “care for history education” should be self-evident, systematic and comprehensive so that history as a school subject can fulfil its social function.⁵ At the same time, it should reflect the current state of knowledge in history didactics and in historical research – at least within the European context, and ideally in a global one. When considering these issues, we inevitably arrive at crucial questions for high-quality history teaching: What is the concept behind the state curriculum for the subject of history in the Slovak Republic? And how do political elites – who, through their decisions, have long allocated only one or two weekly lessons to the study of history – approach its “necessity” for maintaining democratic society?⁶

This, in turn, raises two sub-questions:

1. Do we have any actual concept for developing the educational standard for history, or is it merely a matter of chronology and complexity?
2. What is, in fact, the meaning of learning about the past?

The Anthropocene and the Reconsideration of Historical Thinking

The instructional figures and project-based teaching units analysed in this study can be interpreted within the broader scholarly debate on the Anthropocene, which in contemporary literature is understood not only as a potential new geological epoch, but also as an epistemological and interpretative framework that fundamentally

³ BENEŠ, *Společnost, vědomí, dějiny*, 5–19.

⁴ For a more detailed discussion of the factors influencing the quality of history education in Slovakia, see BOJKOVÁ, *Dejepis globálne*, 6–54.

⁵ According to the Innovated State Educational Programme, the primary function of history as a school subject is “to cultivate the historical consciousness of students as whole personalities and to preserve the continuity of historical memory in the sense of transmitting historical experience – whether from local, regional, national, European or global perspectives. The transmission of this experience primarily involves the gradual learning of those historical events, phenomena and processes in time and space that have fundamentally influenced the development of Slovak and global society and have been reflected in the image of our present.” For further reference, see: *Educational Standard for History for Lower Secondary Education*, iŠVP, https://www.statpedu.sk/files/articles/dokumenty/inovovany-statny-vzdelavaci-program/dejepis_nsv_2014.pdf.

⁶ The current valid Framework Educational Plan (RUP), which determines the number of hours allocated to each subject across levels of education, specifies the following for history: Primary schools: 6 teaching hours for grades 5–9; Eight-year grammar schools: 5 teaching hours for grades 1–4; Four-year grammar schools and eight-year grammar schools (upper stage): 6 teaching hours for grades 1–4 (equivalent to grades 5–8 of the eight-year programme); Bilingual grammar schools: 5 teaching hours for grades 1–5. For more details, see: <https://www.statpedu.sk/sk/svp/inovovany-statny-vzdelavaci-program/ramcovy-ucebny-plan/>; <https://www.statpedu.sk/sk/svp/inovovany-statny-vzdelavaci-program/inovovany-svp-gymnazia-osemrocny-vzdelavacim-programom/>.

transforms the way history, historical causality and human agency are conceptualized.⁷ The concept of the Anthropocene draws attention to the fact that human societies have become a geological force capable of influencing key planetary systems such as climate, hydrological cycles and biodiversity.⁸ This shift simultaneously challenges the traditional dichotomies between nature and society that are deeply embedded in classical narratives of historical knowledge. Dipesh Chakrabarty argues that the Anthropocene disrupts the foundational assumptions of modern historical thinking, particularly the separation of human history from the history of the Earth.⁹ In the Anthropocene, these two dimensions increasingly intersect, requiring new forms of historical interpretation capable of addressing the interrelations between social, political and environmental processes.¹⁰

From the perspective of history education, this implies the need to move beyond an understanding of history limited to a sequence of political events and actors, and to incorporate environmental conditions, material infrastructures and the long-term consequences of human intervention in the landscape into historical analysis. Such an approach corresponds with the aim of this study to demonstrate that history education grounded in a meta-level learning about the past – one to which students have a lived and present relationship – is not only possible but also didactically productive. Concepts of studying the past that go beyond traditional emphases on chronology and complexity, and that offer alternative perspectives on the role and function of the historical sciences – and consequently on the practical dimension of history, which is also emphasized in history didactics – were prominently discussed at the World Congress of Historical Sciences held in Poznań in August 2022.¹¹ These include research areas experimenting with non-anthropocentric, non-European and non-secular approaches, such as stratigraphic Anthropocene, ecocide, epistemicide, planetary history, animal history, plant history, new environmental history, new history of things, post-secular history, post-human/ist history, sonic history, sensory history, and big and deep history.

One may debate the relevance of some of these modern trends in historical research, or the blurring of boundaries between nature and culture, and the non-anthropocentric interpretation of history. Yet, for school history education in Slovakia, the more pressing issue is to what extent these concepts – each of which significantly redefines the function of the past in our present – are reflected in the state curriculum. Do we, as historians, didacticians, and history teachers – the key actors in shaping historical consciousness in Slovak society – reflect on what and why our students should be learning in history? Does the content of school history respond to the needs of our present? Should it? And if not, what aspects of learning about the past are constant, enduring, ever-present? Do these aspects appear in our curriculum – or are we still teaching the past for the sake of the past?

7 CRUTZEN – STOERMER, *The "Anthropocene"*, 17–18; BONNEUIL – FRESSOZ, *The Shock of the Anthropocene*.

8 CRUTZEN, *Geology of mankind*, 23.

9 CHAKRABARTY, *The Climate of History*, 197–222.

10 CHAKRABARTY, *Climate and Capital*, 1–26.

11 *XXIII International Congress of Historical Sciences (IChS)*, <https://www.cish.org/index.php/en/congresses-meetings/poznan-2020-2022/>.

History as Tradition and History as Reaction

The questions raised above reveal history education in a dual perspective: history as tradition and history as reaction. The term *tradition* (from the Latin *tradere / traditum*) in its broadest sense simply means everything that is transmitted or handed down from the past to the present, from one generation to the next. It encompasses all that a society of a given time possesses – everything that already existed when its current members entered it – and which is not merely the product of physical processes in the external world or the exclusive result of ecological or physiological necessity.¹² In this context, and from the perspective of methods and approaches long applied in the Slovak educational environment, history as tradition means a chronological and factual understanding of history teaching, oriented primarily toward political history. Viliam Kratochvíl reminds us that chronology is undoubtedly the guiding thread of history education, yet we must not overvalue it, since it often gives rise to the “weaknesses of factual and chronological history teaching”.¹³ The traditional emphasis on political history in Slovakia is, in turn, related to the long-term underfunding of lesson hours for the subject of history (the lowest among EU countries). As a result, the content of school history focuses on the bare minimum, leaving out essential areas such as social history, the history of everyday life, regional history and environmental topics. However, tradition inherently carries within itself the potential for change. Traditions evolve because they are never quite satisfactory for some of those who inherit them.¹⁴ In contemporary educational discourse, far greater emphasis is placed on the creative capacities of students, on spontaneity and on the ability to discover one’s “true self” and to build one’s “own identity” – all with the aim of consciously detaching from traditional rules and beliefs.¹⁵

History as a response to tradition moves away from pure chronology. It strives instead for thematic instruction, focuses on the development of broader competences rather than the mechanical acquisition of facts, and incorporates elements of constructivist pedagogy, which in recent years has faced significant criticism.¹⁶ This oscillation of history education between these two poles weakens the potential of learning about the past. The traditional model, still dominant in Slovak schools, is criticized for its insufficient connection to the needs of our present, while the complete rejection of tradition often places factual knowledge in opposition to understanding, critical thinking, creativity and the search for meaning.¹⁷ Into this discussion, Viliam Kratochvíl has made a significant and much-needed contribution through his unique Slovak work *The Metaphor of the Tree as a Model of History Didactics*.¹⁸ He proposes a balanced model of history teaching that combines “history as tradition” and “history as reaction”. His concept of history instruction is based on the meta-level of learning about the past – that is, on identifying what is constant, enduring and always present

12 SHILS, *Tradition*, 12.

13 KRATOCHVÍL, *Metafora stromu*, 28.

14 SHILS, *Tradition*, 214–215.

15 *Ibidem*, 28.

16 American professor and literary theorist E.D. Hirsch observes that there is a direct correlation between the introduction of constructivism in the United States and France and the deterioration of students’ academic performance. For more details, see: WIKFORSS, *Alternatívne fakty*, 147–153.

17 *Ibidem*, 152.

18 KRATOCHVÍL, *Metafora stromu*.

in history education, while simultaneously presenting a form of teaching that renders the past tangible and relevant for students in understanding the contemporary world. He encourages us to view traditional chronology through the lens of fundamental categories that are essential for learning about history – categories that cannot be fully understood without chronology: time, space, society, economy, government/power, change/continuity, reality/fiction, right/wrong and one final category that reflects the teacher’s overall approach to history – engaging/boring.¹⁹ These categories serve as the core elements of the dimensions of historical consciousness, representing the cognitive operations through which we can use historical knowledge to navigate the present.²⁰

In the Slovak context, where traditional history teaching still predominates, these ideas may seem abstract. Yet, their application through specific topics and instructional figures can provide a fully comprehensive picture of a form of history education that cultivates in students a lived, present relationship with the past – as Viliam Kratochvíl continually emphasizes in his work.²¹ The instructional figures presented deliberately combine “tradition” and “response” in history education as two indispensable dimensions of historical learning. Tradition represents an anchoring in the discipline of history – particularly in working with time, continuity, change and historical interpretation. Reaction, by contrast, reflects the need to address contemporary global challenges, including the environmental crisis and the ongoing debate on the Anthropocene. This balanced approach makes it possible to preserve the disciplinary identity of history while simultaneously strengthening its social relevance. History education thus does not become a tool of normative environmental education, but rather a space for the critical interpretation of the relationship between humans, nature and society from a historical perspective. It is precisely at this point that the Anthropocene becomes a functional framework for the meta-level of learning about the past, which is also pursued by this study. The meta-level enables students not only to learn about past events, but also to reflect on why and how we think about the past, what questions we pose to it, and what meanings we attribute to it in the present. In this sense, the Anthropocene does not represent another “topic” of history education, but rather a way of connecting the past with the lived experience of the contemporary world.

Rivers as Living Entities with Their Own Rights

From 22 to 24 March 2023, the UN Water Conference²² was held in New York, where a coalition of governments launched the so-called Freshwater Challenge – the largest initiative in history to restore degraded rivers, lakes and wetlands, which are central to addressing the escalating global crises in water, climate and biodiversity. The goal of this initiative is to restore 300,000 kilometres of rivers – more than seven times the Earth’s circumference – and 350 million hectares of wetlands (an area larger than India) by 2030.²³

19 Ibidem, 22.

20 Ibidem, 17.

21 Ibidem.

22 *UN 2023 Water Conference*, <https://sdgs.un.org/conferences/water2023>.

23 *Largest river and wetland restoration initiative in history launched at UN Water Conference*, <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/press-release/largest-river-and-wetland-restoration-initiative-history-launched-un>.

The conference yielded several important conclusions:

- Approximately 4 billion people, or about half of the world's population, experience severe water scarcity for at least one month each year.
- 2.3 billion people, nearly one-quarter of the global population, live in countries suffering from water shortages.
- Nearly three-quarters of all recent natural disasters are related to water, including floods, droughts and storms. These disasters have destroyed lives and livelihoods, affected millions of people and caused an estimated 700 billion USD in economic losses over the past two decades.
- By 2050, areas facing "extreme drought" are expected to increase fivefold, 5.7 billion people are likely to live in regions with water shortages, and the number of people at risk of flooding may rise to approximately 1.6 billion.²⁴

As a result of these alarming facts, a global movement for river protection has been gaining momentum in recent years. This movement has led to a growing number of rivers being recognized as living entities endowed with certain rights – or even with legal personhood.²⁵ One example is the Magpie River in Quebec, Canada, which has been legally recognized as a person since February 2021. Local authorities have granted it nine rights, including the right to flow, the right to be free from pollution and the right to stand in court.²⁶ This initiative is part of a global environmental movement that began when Ecuador, in 2008, became the first country to enshrine the rights of nature in its constitution. Comparable legislative mechanisms were later adopted by Bolivia, Mexico and Colombia, which granted rights to the Amazon River, the largest river in the world. Other countries, including New Zealand, Australia and Bangladesh, have joined the movement, focusing primarily on the legal rights of rivers. In the United States, the Klamath River has been recognized as a legal person, and Lake Erie has also been granted rights.²⁷ The conferral of legal personhood on rivers represents a profound shift away from the deeply entrenched Western belief that humans stand at the top of the natural world. For many Indigenous peoples, however – such as the Māori (the original Polynesian inhabitants of New Zealand), who regard rivers and trees as their ancestors – this concept is nothing new, for "rivers have been here long before us, and therefore they deserve the right to live".²⁸ Granting rights to non-human entities thus connects Western and Indigenous legal systems, with the aim of translating Indigenous law into the language of the Western world.²⁹

24 Ibidem.

25 For further discussion of this issue, see: O'DONNELL, *Legal Rights for Rivers*.

26 BARCKHAM, *Should rivers have*.

27 BERGE, *This Canadian river*; BARCKHAM, *Should rivers have*.

28 BERGE, *This Canadian river*.

29 Ibidem.

This framework was articulated in the Brisbane Declaration, adopted in 2007³⁰ and revised in 2018,³¹ which presented 35 practical recommendations to promote and advance the implementation of environmental water flows³² through legislation, regulation, water management programmes and research. For the reasons mentioned above, the modern conception of water – as a substance abstracted from social, cultural and religious contexts – is increasingly being questioned. This shift has intensified scholarly interest in studying water not only as a natural phenomenon but also as a historical, political and cultural one. Consequently, greater attention is now being given to alternative approaches to understanding water, beyond the predominantly ecohydrological methods used in the past. This has led to a deeper recognition of the complex interrelationships between water, society and ecosystem processes, grounded in the fundamental idea that water systems (such as rivers) and human societies co-evolve, continuously shaping one another through their interconnectedness in space and time.³³

Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development and History

In the context of history education, the so-called *modern* conception of water – as something historical, political and cultural – paradoxically appears traditional. Recognizing the interdependence between historical space and the way of life and livelihood of people and societies has long been an essential disciplinary competence in learning about the past, specifically in understanding how to work with historical space.³⁴ A concrete example is the topic of river civilizations, through which students around the world learn about the close connection between rivers and human existence in antiquity (in the Slovak context, this topic appears in the sixth grade of secondary school, that is, among 10–11-year-old students). However, the true importance of history education for our present and future becomes even more apparent when analysed within the framework of the United Nations global environmental programme on sustainable development, which also addresses the protection of water systems as discussed above. In this context, the key document is Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development, which outlines 17 strategic goals and 169 sub-targets, integrated into three dimensions of sustainability: economic, social and environmental. The preamble to Agenda 2030 declares that, as nations united under the United Nations (including the Slovak Republic): “We are determined to free the human race from the tyranny of poverty and want and to heal and secure our planet. We are resolved to take the bold and transformative steps which are urgently needed to shift the world onto

30 *The Brisbane Declaration (2007)*. 10th International Riversymposium and International Environmental Flows Conference, 3–6 September 2007 (Brisbane, Australia). The conference brought together over 800 scientists, economists, engineers, managers, and policymakers representing 57 nations, <https://riverfoundation.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/THE-BRISBANE-DECLARATION.pdf>.

31 *The Brisbane Declaration and Global Action Agenda on Environmental Flows (2018)*, <https://riversymposium.com/about/brisbane-declaration/>.

32 *The revised 2018 Brisbane Declaration* defines the term *environmental flow* as: “The quantity, timing, and quality of freshwater flows and levels necessary to sustain aquatic ecosystems, which in turn support human cultures, economies, sustainable livelihoods, and well-being.”

33 ANDERSON – JACKSON – THARME et al. *Understanding rivers*.

34 This disciplinary competence is also part of the currently valid educational standard for history at both the primary and secondary school levels in the Slovak Republic. For further details, see: *Educational Standard for History for Lower Secondary Education, iŠVP*, p. 4, https://www.statpedu.sk/files/articles/dokumenty/inovovany-statny-vzdelavaci-program/dejepis_nsv_2014.pdf.

a sustainable and resilient path.”³⁵ This vision is to be realized through the gradual fulfilment of 17 key goals:

No poverty ~ Zero hunger ~ Good health and well-being ~ Quality education ~ Gender equality ~ Clean water and sanitation ~ Affordable and clean energy ~ Decent work and economic growth ~ Industry, innovation, and infrastructure ~ Reduced inequalities ~ Sustainable cities and communities ~ Responsible consumption and production ~ Climate action ~ Life below water ~ Life on land ~ Peace, justice, and strong institutions ~ Partnerships for the goals.³⁶

Humanity develops in time and space, and every global problem faced by society today has its historical context. Therefore, history – as the institutionalized form of engaging with the past – is inherently global. It teaches students to perceive both the past and the present from a global perspective, cultivating an awareness of historicity – that is, of the human presence in history and its impact on both the immediate and distant environment. In doing so, history education naturally encourages students to form attitudes toward the positive and negative consequences of human actions.³⁷ These and other qualities of history education demonstrate that learning about the past plays an irreplaceable role in shaping our future. With specific regard to Goal 4 of Agenda 2030 – Quality Education,³⁸ it is appropriate to discuss to what extent the design of the state curriculum in Slovakia reflects the global challenges of the contemporary world (as represented, for example, by Agenda 2030, to which the Slovak Republic has committed itself as a UN member). At the same time, it is worth asking to what extent the time allocation for history lessons reflects the potential of history education. Does the potential of learning about the past translate into school practice? Is such an approach to history teaching present and feasible in Slovak schools today?

I addressed the potential and limitations of history education in relation to its implementation in school practice in an earlier study entitled “Global History”.³⁹ Therefore, in this paper, I do not attempt to duplicate that analysis or to answer the question posed at the very beginning – namely, what is the concept of state curriculum development and what place do social, regional and environmental topics hold within it. This issue requires a separate, detailed analysis, which I intend to undertake in future research. Nor do I attempt to determine whether the global dimension of history and its connection to the present are adequately reflected in Slovak schools, as we currently lack empirical research with sufficient explanatory power. My objective

35 *Preamble of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. For more information, see: <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>.

36 Further details available at: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>.

37 BOJKOVÁ, *Dejepis globálne*, 6–54 (article is available also online at: https://www.nadaciapontis.sk/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/Pontis_RV4_2019_WEB.pdf).

38 “By 2030, ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture’s contribution to sustainable development.” For more information, see: <https://www.unep.org/topics/sustainable-development-goals/why-do-sustainable-development-goals-matter/goal-4-quality>.

39 BOJKOVÁ, *Dejepis globálne*.

here is to demonstrate – through the instructional figures I have developed – that history instruction based on the meta-level of learning about the past, to which students develop a lived and present relationship, while also reflecting global contemporary issues, is both achievable and meaningful. In the following section, I present instructional figures that balance “tradition” and “reaction” within history education – two essential components of the continuous questioning of the purpose and meaning of learning about the past. The aim of the presented concept, through the eco-educational project *The Story of the River* (Príbeh rieky),⁴⁰ is primarily to develop core disciplinary competences in history education⁴¹ and, secondarily, to direct students’ attention toward the river – not only as an object of study in the natural sciences but also as an entity that connects people, places and other forms of life, inspiring and sustaining various cultural patterns, values and ways of living.⁴²

The Story of the River as a Didactic Response to the Anthropocene

The instructional figures presented in this study may be understood as a didactic response to the challenges of the Anthropocene, as they are based on locally embedded case studies (river, landscape, region) that enable students to analyse the interconnections between human action and natural systems from a historical perspective. Emphasis is placed on place (town/village) and region – while also situating these within the broader context of landscape – where students live and experience everyday relationships,⁴³ with the aim of exploring historical space while simultaneously adopting a non-anthropocentric perspective on their immediate surroundings. The starting point for the development of the instructional figures is the river as a spatial entity present in every region.⁴⁴ This makes it possible to apply the proposed instructional figures practically anywhere within the territory of Slovakia (and, in principle, wherever a river is present), thereby creating a universal concept for history education that remains at the same time deeply and concretely connected to the specific place or region in which students live. In this sense, the instructional figures combine transferability with contextual specificity, allowing students to engage with broader historical and environmental processes through familiar, lived spaces. Rivers were here before people and human settlements, and they will be here after us. However, the emergence and development of human settlements is inevitably linked to the existence of rivers, and without them, human settlements would probably not have arisen. Nevertheless, we observe an ambivalent relationship between rivers and human settlements, where on the one hand, the river appears in relation to human settlements as an existential element, life-giving water, and on the other hand, often as an obstacle that must be overcome or used to one’s advantage, regardless of the consequences it may have on the life of the river and, ultimately, on the whole of

40 Ecological-educational television programme for students, teachers and parents. Available at: <https://www.rtvs.sk/televizia/archiv/18080/302776>.

41 For more information, see: *Educational Standard for History for Lower Secondary Education, iŠVP, 3–6*, available at: https://www.statpedu.sk/files/articles/dokumenty/inovovany-statny-vzdelavaci-program/dejepis_nsv_2014.pdf.

42 ANDERSON – JACKSON – THARME et al. *Understanding Rivers*.

43 KRATOCHVÍL, *Metafora stromu*, 31.

44 For a more detailed discussion of the concept of *region* in historical, geographical, and educational contexts, see: RIUKULEHTO, *Various Directions in Regional History* (article is available also online at: <https://helda.helsinki.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/6ff94128-a436-4b00-ab4b-5c742f949dfa/content>).

humanity. By travelling along the river and through its surroundings, we get to know the place and region in which we live, and at the same time we learn to perceive the river in the first place, and then to perceive it not only as something natural, but also as something historical, political and cultural.

A concrete implementation of this conceptual framework is represented by the eco-educational project *The Story of the River*, which “responds to what has been described as a “crisis of perception” and a world saturated with disinformation” by producing engaging audiovisual content in the form of a television series.⁴⁵ The concept was developed by filmmaker Palo Pekarčík, and the project is produced by Partizánfilm and the Association TVORenie, in cooperation with STVR and experts from the academic, scientific and non-profit sectors. To date, more than sixty prominent female and male scientists, researchers, activists and witnesses have participated in the project. Together, they guide students along the river basins of Slovakia, introduce them to scientific work, conduct experiments and encourage playful and active engagement with local content. Through the interdisciplinary exploration of rivers and their basins, young people become acquainted with scientific disciplines and fundamental research methods, while simultaneously discovering the importance of what quietly flows beside us. So far, three series have been broadcast, mapping the stories of the Hornád, Poprad and Hron rivers. The conducted experiments span a wide spectrum of disciplines – from ecology, biology, geology, geography, chemistry, physics and astronomy to the humanities and social sciences, including sociology, anthropology, ethics and history.

The instructional figures⁴⁶ presented in this study focus on the historical context of rivers and are connected to the Hornád River basin. Therefore, each of them includes a corresponding time sequence from the series *The Story of the Hornád River (Príbeh rieky Hornád)*. In addition to the river itself, these instructional figures concentrate on notable sites and phenomena across the entire basin, while remaining universal and applicable to the study of any watercourse. Each corresponding episode of the series may serve as either a guide for conducting an experiment or simply as inspiration for creating and implementing one. The selected instructional figures explore the relationship between the river and humans, representing inquiries into vanished settlements, chapels or pilgrimage sites, technical monuments and traditions, as well as problems and challenges within the basin of a specific river. The river is not presented here as a passive backdrop to human action, but rather as an active agent shaping economic, social and cultural patterns of life over the long term. Such an approach corresponds with environmental history as well as with theoretical strands that emphasize the agency of non-human actors – particularly natural elements such as rivers or landscapes – in historical processes.⁴⁷ Bruno Latour has pointed out that modern societies have systematically obscured this relationality through the concept of “nature” as a passive background, a notion fundamentally challenged by the Anthropocene.⁴⁸ This perspective aligns with post humanist and new materialist theories, which stress that historical processes emerge from interactions between

45 For further details, see: <https://pribehrieky.sk/>.

46 The teaching figures are part of an extensive methodological resource created for the individual episodes of the series, intended for the use of students and teachers at primary and secondary schools.

47 LATOUR, *Reassembling the Social*; HARAWAY, *Staying with the Trouble*.

48 LATOUR, *Reassembling the Social*; HARAWAY, *Staying with the Trouble*.

humans, technologies and material environments. Donna Haraway argues that the Anthropocene calls for new narratives of *coexistence* (“staying with the trouble”) that transcend linear and anthropocentric understandings of history.⁴⁹ Instructional figures grounded in place-based learning create space for such forms of historical thinking by guiding students to reflect on the relationships between the past, the present and the future consequences of human action.

Instructional Figures: Didactic and Methodological Foundations

The analysed educational activities take the form of instructional figures and project-oriented teaching units that extend beyond the framework of a single lesson and are designed as complex didactic structures. They are primarily anchored in history education, while demonstrating a strong interdisciplinary overlap with environmental education, civic education, regional education, media literacy and historical literacy.⁵⁰ The instructional figures are primarily intended for lower secondary education (ISCED 2) and upper secondary education (ISCED 3), with the possibility of adaptation for non-formal and community-based educational settings. The activities are conceived as multi-lesson educational projects, often implemented over several weeks, which allows for the gradual development of students’ analytical and interpretative competences. The dominant thematic areas include the relationship between humans and space or landscape, historical memory and its social formation, environmental and social history, the interconnection of local history with global historical processes, and continuity and discontinuity in historical development. The instructional figures are grounded in a constructivist didactic approach, the principles of place-based education, an emphasis on the active interpretation of historical phenomena, and work with authentic historical and environmental problems. Regarding methods, emphasis is placed on the analysis of concrete historical cases, the interpretation of local history, discussion of historical and value-based questions, problem-oriented project work, and reflective and argumentative activities.

The Story of the River may be understood as a long-term thematic project that connects environmental history with regional history, uses local realities as a starting point for historical inquiry and supports the development of historical literacy and civic awareness. In terms of expected learning outcomes, the instructional figures focus on the development of historical literacy, critical thinking, the ability to interpret historical narratives, an understanding of the relationship between past, present and future, and the development of students’ value orientation and civic engagement.

The main objective of the analysed instructional figures is to develop students’ historical thinking and historical literacy through the meta-level of learning about the past, enabling them to connect historical knowledge with their own lived experience, the local environment and current social and environmental challenges of the contemporary world. This overarching objective is realized through the following partial objectives:

1. Cognitive Objectives

- to develop an understanding of fundamental historical categories (time, change, continuity, historical causality, perspective)

⁴⁹ HARAWAY, *Staying with the Trouble*.

⁵⁰ SEIXAS – MORTON, *The Big Six Historical Thinking Concepts*.

- to guide students towards interpreting historical sources within their social, cultural and environmental contexts
 - to support the ability to analyse long-term historical processes and their consequences for the present
 - to develop the ability to connect local history with regional, national and global historical processes
2. Competence-Based (Procedural) Objectives
 - to develop the ability to formulate historical questions and hypotheses
 - to guide students in working with diverse types of sources (textual, visual, cartographic, oral, material)
 - to support argumentation, discussion and critical reflection on historical narratives
 - to develop collaboration, project planning and the presentation of results
 3. Affective and Value-Oriented Objectives
 - to support a lived relationship to the past through locally embedded themes
 - to develop responsibility for shared cultural and natural heritage
 - to foster a sensitive perception of relationships between humans, landscape and society
 - to strengthen civic engagement and interest in public space
 4. Metacognitive Objectives (Meta-Level of Learning)
 - to develop the ability to reflect on one's own learning and understanding of the past
 - to guide students towards recognizing the constructed nature of historical narratives
 - to support the ability to evaluate the significance of the past for orientation in the contemporary world
 - to develop critical thinking in relation to public representations of history
 5. Environmental and Interdisciplinary Objectives
 - to develop an understanding of the interconnection between historical processes and environmental change
 - to guide students towards perceiving rivers, landscapes and environments as historical actors
 - to support interdisciplinary links between history, geography, biology, civic education and environmental education
 - to develop the ability to think complexly about human–nature relationships over the long term

Bloom's Taxonomy and the Development of Historical Thinking

The instructional figures presented are based on systematic work across different cognitive levels of learning, which can be interpreted through Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives. Bloom's taxonomy, originally formulated as a hierarchical model of cognitive processes, provides a didactic framework that makes it possible to analyse not only the scope of acquired knowledge, but also the depth of understanding and the level of thinking to which students are guided.⁵¹ In the context of history education, Bloom's taxonomy is particularly relevant because it allows for a distinction between the reproductive learning of historical facts and the development of complex

⁵¹ BLOOM (ed.), *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives*.

historical thinking based on interpretation, evaluation and the construction of historical meaning.⁵² The analysed instructional figures are designed to systematically move beyond lower cognitive levels and towards higher-order cognitive processes.

At the levels of remembering and understanding, the instructional figures work with basic historical concepts, temporal orientation and factual knowledge related to the local context (river, landscape, region). These levels do not constitute an independent goal of instruction but rather serve as a starting point for further analytical and interpretative work. In line with contemporary history didactics, factual knowledge is functionally integrated into broader questions about the meaning of the past, thereby eliminating isolated memorization.⁵³

At the levels of application and analysis, the instructional figures guide students to use historical knowledge in solving concrete problems and to analyse relationships between human action and natural conditions from a historical perspective. Students work with historical sources, maps, visual materials and local narratives, and are guided to identify causes, consequences and long-term processes. This level corresponds to an understanding of historical thinking as the ability to analyse the past in terms of relationships rather than as a sequence of isolated events.⁵⁴ At the same time, it creates space for linking local history with regional and global processes, including environmental changes characteristic of the Anthropocene.

The highest cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy – evaluation and creation – play a key role in the analysed instructional figures. Students are guided to evaluate historical interpretations, compare different narratives of the past and create their own outputs (projects, presentations, public exhibitions) that reflect the significance of the past for the present. This level of learning is closely connected to the meta-level of learning about the past, as students not only work with historical content but also reflect on the process of historical knowledge production itself – that is, why and how we think about the past.⁵⁵ In the context of the Anthropocene, the evaluative and creative dimensions of learning are also linked to reflection on human responsibility towards the natural and cultural environment over the long term.

In connection with the theoretical framework of the Anthropocene, Bloom's taxonomy functions not merely as a tool for classifying educational objectives, but as a means of systematically developing complex historical thinking. It enables students to move gradually from understanding the past to its critical evaluation and creative interpretation in relation to contemporary global challenges. In this context, Bloom's taxonomy becomes a didactic bridge between the traditional aims of history education and the need to respond to the complexity of the Anthropocene.⁵⁶

52 ANDERSON – KRATHWOHL (eds), *A Taxonomy for Learning*.

53 WINEBURG, *Historical Thinking*.

54 LÉVESQUE, *Thinking Historically*.

55 RÜSEN, *Historische Vernunft*.

56 LATOUR, *Down to Earth*.

I. THE CITY AND THE RIVER: EVERYTHING IS CONNECTED

Didactic Tools: internet, coloured pens/markers.

Instructional Figure:

1. Compare the historical map of Košice from 1912 with the current map and find what significant change has occurred in relation to the Hornád River. Mark the change on the current map in blue.

Figure 1: Map of Košice from 1912⁵⁸

Figure 2: Map of Košice from 2025⁵⁹

⁵⁷ Mlynský náhon, o. z., https://mlynskynahon.sk/galeria/#group_363-8.

⁵⁸ Google Maps, https://www.google.com/maps/@48.729258,21.257445,14.06z?entry=ttu&g_ep=EgoyMDI1MDcwOS4wLXkxMDS0ASAFQAw%3D%3D.

2. The attached photo is a current photo of the Jakab Palace, which was the residence of the President of Czechoslovakia, Edvard Beneš, in 1945:
 - Circle Jakab's Palace on the current map of Košice from the first task.
 - In the gallery on the website of the Mlynský náhon⁵⁹ civic association, find a historical photo of Jakab's Palace from a similar perspective and insert/paste it into the worksheet.
 - based on the information from the video preview *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 7, time 16:45–19:00, decide which of the views of Mlynský náhon appeared to President Edvard Beneš when he went out onto the balcony of Jakab's Palace.
 - Imagine that President Edvard Beneš had again stayed in Jakab's Palace today. From the position of Edvard Beneš, write a short status update for posting on a social network in which you express his opinion on the current appearance of Mlynský náhon.

Figure 3: Jacob's Palace today

Figure 4: Historical photo of Jakab's Palace

3. Study the website of the Mlynský náhon civic association⁶² and discuss the civic initiative to return Hornád to the city and its goals.
4. Use the information from the video presentation *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 7, time 3:30–16:45 and explain how the life of bats, insects and other plants and animals is connected to the river in the city.
5. Browse through the winning proposal of the landscape and urban planning competition Revitalization of the Mlynský náhon in Košice⁶³ and assess how the

59 Gallery Mlynský náhon, o. z., <https://mlynskynahon.sk/galeria/>.

60 Street View – Jakab's Palace, https://www.google.com/maps/@48.7211644,21.2649426,3a,75y,90h,69.53t/data=!3m7!1e1!3m5!1sHlONMGaZ9K6UPSYC5CdQ2Q!2e0!6shttps:%2F%2Fstreetviewpixels-pa.googleapis.com%2Fv1%2Fthumbnail%3Fcb_client%3Dmaps_sv.tactile%26w%3D900%26h%3D600%26pitch%3D20.46608531276584%26panoid%3DHlONMGaZ9K6UPSYC5CdQ2Q%26yaw%3D90!7i16384!8i8192?entry=ttu&g_ep=EgoyMDI1MDcwOS4wLkxMDSoASAFQAw%3D%3D

61 Gallery Mlynský náhon, o. z., <https://mlynskynahon.sk/galeria/>.

62 Mlynský náhon, o. z., www.mlynskynahon.sk.

63 Mlynský náhon, o. z. *Hanáček*, <https://mlynskynahon.sk/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Hanacek.pdf>.

revitalization of waterways can affect the quality of life of residents in cities in general.

6. In 2020, the Universal Declaration of River Rights⁶⁴ was issued, which stipulates that all rivers must have at least the following basic rights: the right to flow, the right to perform essential functions within their ecosystem, the right not to be polluted, the right to nourish and be nourished by sustainable water-permeable layers, the right to original biodiversity and the right to regeneration and restoration. State the possible reasons that led to the decision to grant rivers fundamental rights for the first time in history and formulate your own opinion on this initiative.
7. Investigate whether the fundamental rights of the nearest watercourse in your area are being respected in accordance with the adopted Universal Declaration of the Rights of Rivers, write a short report on your findings and propose possible solutions to any violations of the declared rights found.

II. THE RIVER IN THE LIVES OF OUR ANCESTORS⁶⁵

Didactic Tools: *a map of the respective town/village with the river marked, a camera/phone/voice recorder for making video or audio recordings, a photo album or notebook for collecting historical photographs.*

Instructional Figure:

1. Find the oldest living witness in your family, village or town.
2. On a prepared map, sketch a timeline from the present day back to the founding or first written record of your town or village.
3. On the timeline, mark the birth year of the witness you selected.
4. Take inspiration from the video excerpt *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 1, time 11:35–2:58 and create your own list of interview questions for your chosen witness on the topic “The River in the Lives of Our Ancestors”.
5. Based on your list of questions, record a short video interview with your chosen witness.
6. Use the information from the recording to compare how the residents of your town or village related to the river in the past and how they do so today.
7. Evaluate how these findings are reflected in the current life, appearance and overall condition of the river and its surroundings.

III. CHAPLES AND PLACES OF PILGRIMAGE⁶⁶

Didactic Tools: *a map of the built-up area and surrounding landscape of the town/village, a notebook, a device for photographic documentation (camera or mobile phone), internet access.*

Instructional Figure:

1. Define the meaning of the word *patrocinium* (church dedication).
2. Locate the nearest chapel, pilgrimage site or statue of a saint in your area. Mark it on the map of your town or village and find out its corresponding *patrocinium*.
3. Analyse the respective *patrocinium* and interpret its meaning.
4. Take inspiration from the video excerpt *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode VI, time 0:35–02:44. Examine the chapel, pilgrimage site or statue from an architectural

⁶⁴ *The Universal Declaration of the Rights of Rivers*, <https://www.rightsofrivers.org/#declaration>.

⁶⁵ Time sequence in the series: *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 1, time 11:35–12:58.

⁶⁶ Time sequence in the series: *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 6, time 0:35–02:44.

perspective and, based on available materials, write a short report including information such as: who designed or built it, who financed the construction, when it was built, in what architectural style, what materials were used etc.

5. Evaluate the current condition of the chapel, pilgrimage site or statue and propose possible ways to improve it.
6. Assess to what extent the chapel, pilgrimage site or statue is an active part of the spiritual life of your community and identify possible reasons for the current situation.
7. Generalize the significance of the construction of chapels, pilgrimage sites and statues of saints within the territory of Slovakia.
8. Create an interactive map of chapels, pilgrimage sites or statues of saints in your district or region or throughout Slovakia.

IV. EXTINCT SETTLEMENTS⁶⁷

Didactic Tools: *Internet, a device for creating photo or video documentation (mobile phone, camera etc.).*

Instructional Figure:

1. Search available sources to find a list of extinct villages on the territory of Slovakia.
2. From the list, select the nearest extinct village in relation to your place of residence or school.
3. Investigate the reason for the disappearance of the selected village.
4. Use the video excerpt *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 5, time 8:30–16:47 and organize a historical field trip to the site of the extinct village. Create photo or video documentation from the excursion and write a short article about it. Try to publish the article in the local newspaper or on the website of your school, town or municipality.
5. Take inspiration from the Czech application *Zaniklé obce a staré mapy (Extinct Villages and Old Maps)* and, using freely available tools, design your own interactive website or application that includes all extinct villages/towns in Slovakia.
6. Use social media to inform classmates across Slovakia about your created website or application and encourage them to contribute content related to each extinct village.

V. RIVER, MAN, WORK AND TIME⁶⁸

Didactic Tools: *a device for photo or video documentation, internet access, a pen, a notebook.*

Instructional Figure:

1. Define the term *technical monument*.
2. In the Register of National Cultural Monuments (NNKP)⁶⁹ find the nearest technical monument in your area.
3. Gather basic information about the selected technical monument and use photos or video recordings to document its current condition.

⁶⁷ Time sequence in the series: *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 5, time 8:30–16:47.

⁶⁸ Time sequence in the series: *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 7, time 4:43–12:02; *The Story of the Hornád River*, entire episode 8.

⁶⁹ *Register of Immovable National Cultural Monuments (NNKP)*, <https://www.pamiatky.sk/evidencie-a-registre/register-nnkp>.

4. Find a local witness and, based on the video excerpt *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 7, time 4:43–12:02, record their memories related to the selected technical monument.
5. Using the information collected in tasks 3 and 4, create a PowerPoint or video presentation and present it in class.
6. Compare the video segment about *Štefanská Huta* (*The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 7, time 4:43–12:02) and *The Story of the Hornád River*, entire episode 8, with the following image of Štefanská Huta.⁷⁰ Explain the differences and discuss them.
7. Propose new ways to utilize the technical monument in your area and inform the relevant authorities about your ideas.

Figure 5: Cross-section of the amalgamation building.

Figure 6: Cross-section of the amalgamation building and the café.

⁷⁰ Design proposal for the reconstruction of the Štefanská Ironworks: LELKOVÁ, *Štefanská Ironworks*.

VI. TRADITIONS IN OUR PRESENCE⁷¹

Didactic Tools: *a device for audio, photo or video documentation (mobile phone, camera, voice recorder), internet access.*

Instructional Figure:

1. Record an interview with your parents, grandparents, great-grandparents or elderly residents of your community on the topic "A Tradition or Custom That Has Been Practiced in Our Family or Community for the Longest Time".
2. Support the long-term existence of the described custom or tradition with a specific material, visual or written historical source.
3. From the customs and traditions described, create a class list of all the customs and traditions that exist in your town or village and identify which of them are still practiced today.
4. Take inspiration from the video excerpt *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 9, time 14:54–19:40, and find a suitable place in your town, village or school to establish a "Tradition Room" for your community. Create photo or video documentation of the selected site.
5. Prepare a project about the "Tradition Room" of your town or village, using the materials you collected and the photo/video documentation of the chosen location.
6. Organize an exhibition in your school featuring the collected historical sources and present your created project there.
7. Arrange a discussion with local authorities (such as the municipal council, the building owner or the school principal) about possible ways to use the selected space for establishing a "Tradition Room" (e.g., symbolic rent, annual lease in exchange for renovation etc.).
8. Implement your project and establish the "Tradition Room" of your town or village.

VII. MAPPING OF MINING CITIES⁷²

Didactic Tools: *internet access.*

Instructional Figure:

1. Based on data about the least developed districts of Slovakia, commonly referred to as "hunger valleys", compile a current list of the least developed districts in the Slovak Republic.

The least developed districts are defined based on the unemployment rate. They define those districts in which unemployment is significantly worse than the Slovak average. The least developed districts, (NRO), or also hunger valleys, are the districts of Lučenec, Poltár, Revúca, Rimavská Sobota, Veľký Krtíš (until 2020), Kežmarok, Sabinov, Svidník, Vranov nad Topľou, Rožňava, Sobrance and Trebišov (district numbers 606, 607, 608, 609, 610, 703, 708, 712, 713, 808, 809, 811). In 2017, the districts of Gelnica, Bardejov and Medzilaborce were added, and in 2018, Košice-okolie, Levoča and Snina (district numbers 801, 701, 705 and 806, 704 and 709) and Stropkov and Michalovce (711, 807) were added. In 2020, the Veľký Krtíš district ceased to be the least developed. In 2022, the Stará Ľubovňa district (710) was added. In 2024, the Snina district ceased

⁷¹ Time sequence in the series: *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 9, time 14:54–19:40.

⁷² Time sequence in the series: *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 10, time 4:22–7:50.

to be the least developed. The map shows the 12 original least developed districts in burgundy, the six new NROs from 2017 and 2018 in dark grey and some districts of Western Slovakia and Považie (VRO) in light grey.⁷³

Figure 7: The Least Developed Districts in the Slovak Republic.⁷⁴

2. Compare the list of the least developed districts you have created with the map showing the rate of long-term unemployment in the regions of Slovakia and explain how the labour market influences the development of towns and villages.

www.iz.sk/sr
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Figure 8: Rate of Long-Term Unemployment in Slovak Regions.⁷⁵

⁷³ *Least Developed Districts*, Institute of Employment, <https://www.iz.sk/sk/projekty/inkluzivny-rast/najmenej-rozvinute-okresy> [accessed 4 October 2025].

⁷⁴ *Ibidem*.

⁷⁵ PÁLENÍK, *Regions of Slovakia*.

3. Identify connections between the results of your previous analysis and the following passage, "The Golden Middle Ages", by historian Dušan Kováč from the book *History of Slovakia*:

The fourteenth and fifteenth centuries were, in both a figurative and literal sense, the golden age of the Kingdom of Hungary. It was a period when gold and silver ore became the foundation of the wealth and prosperity of the Hungarian state. The true golden treasury, where gold and silver were mined, was primarily the territory of present-day Slovakia. At that time, ore was being extracted from all Slovak deposits. In the second half of the fourteenth century, the annual gold production reached around 2,500 kilograms. Most of it came from Slovakia, and the main centre of production was Kremnica. Mining and the development of crafts contributed to the growth of towns. Many settlements had urban characteristics, although not all had privileges confirmed by the king. According to royal decrees, towns with the greatest rights and privileges, called free royal towns, had to be fortified with walls. The most important towns on the present-day territory of Slovakia were Bratislava, Trnava, Košice, Prešov, Bardejov and the free royal mining towns of Banská Štiavnica, Banská Bystrica and Kremnica.⁷⁶

4. Watch the video excerpt *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 10, time 4:22–7:50, and find out how the "Golden Middle Ages" of the Kingdom of Hungary were reflected in the history of the village of Smolník.
5. Based on current regional data available on the website of the Institute of Unemployment,⁷⁷ assess whether the term "golden age" could also describe the present period in Smolník, and justify your conclusion.
6. Considering all previous findings, discuss the possible motivation of Pavol (from the video excerpt *The Story of the Hornád River*, episode 10, time 4:22–7:50) to establish a museum in the former Smolník mine.
7. On the website of the Association of Mining Guilds and Fraternities of Slovakia,⁷⁸ identify other mining towns in Slovakia and determine which of them have established museums in former mines.
8. Create a tourist guide to the mining towns of Slovakia.
9. Using the attached photographs, take a stand on the decline of mining in Slovakia and discuss your opinion.

⁷⁶ KOVÁČ, 39–40.

⁷⁷ *Least Developed Districts*, Institute of Employment, <https://www.iz.sk/sk/projekty/inkluzivny-rast/najmenej-rozvinute-okresy>.

⁷⁸ Association of Mining Guilds and Fraternities of Slovakia, <http://zbsc.eu/mesta.php>.

Figure 9: The end of coal mining in Slovakia.⁸⁰

Figure 10: Organic tomato cultivation in Nováky.⁸¹

Conclusion

The present text and the instructional figures proposed are the result of my long-term and ongoing reflection on the meaning and purpose of history education for our present – and above all for the present of our students. The linkage of the analysed instructional figures with the theoretical framework of the Anthropocene demonstrates that history education can function as a key tool for understanding contemporary planetary challenges without losing its disciplinary identity. In this context, the Anthropocene does not represent merely a thematic expansion of the curriculum, but rather a fundamental shift in how the purpose of historical education is understood. The cognitively sequenced tasks are grounded, at the initial level, in factual knowledge and in the ability to work with information, as reflected in effective verbs derived from Bloom's taxonomy, such as *list*, *select*, *search for*, *define*, *identify*, *trace*, *outline*, *compile* and *design*. At the same time, they motivate students to *compare*, *evaluate*, *assess*, *identify relationships*, *discuss*, *present* the results of their inquiry and even *create* new outputs. Instructional figures designed in this way demonstrate that the development of higher-order cognitive processes is not in contradiction with the discipline of history; on the contrary, it represents its natural realization under the conditions of the contemporary world. The common denominator of all instructional figures is a methodological principle that emphasizes action – an active intervention in real life.⁸¹ The outcome of a history lesson is therefore not only a set of notes and a homework assignment, but, for example, the opportunity to design and create an interactive map and to motivate peers from all over Slovakia to contribute content, or to discuss with local authorities the modern use of dilapidated technical or historical monuments, as well as to initiate the establishment of a local museum. Equally important, however, is the opportunity to observe and explore one's surroundings from a non-anthropocentric perspective – to realize that humans do not stand above nature but, on the contrary, depend on it. Learning the story of a nearby river, for instance by exploring the relationship between the local community and the river in the past and today, may be one of the possible paths to achieving this awareness.

79 Available online: <https://www.codnes.sk/spravy/video-z-bane-novaky-vyviezli-poslednu-tonu-uhlia-tym-sa-definitivne-zavasila-114-rocna-priemyselna-tazba-uhlia-na-slovensku>.

80 Available online: <https://www.hbp.sk/index.php/sk/sluzby/Paradajky>.

81 KRATOCHVÍL, *Metafora stromu*, 31.

A history education capable of responding to these challenges can become an effective tool for addressing global issues not only at the local level but also on national and European scales.

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